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SMART CITY AS AN ALTERNATIVE SOLUTION FOR URBAN DEVELOPMENT AND EQUITY IN INDONESIA

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Community Lifestyle in Post Covid-19 Pandemic

Ahmad Zain Sarnoto

Institut PTIQ Jakarta, Jakarta, Indonesia, Jl. Batan I No. 2 Lebak Bulus, Cilandak,
Kota Jakarta Selatan, DKI Jakarta 12440

E-mail: ahmadzain@ptiq.ac.id

Abstract. The Covid-19 shocked the world upon its existence at the end of 2019. The virus which primarily attacks the respiratory tract, which can lead to death, was first discovered in the city of Wuhan Hubei, province in China. The Covid-19 pandemic outbreak has drastically changed human lifestyle across the world. Most noticeable amongst them is in the economic and livelihood activities, where people are now discouraged or even prohibited to congregate, while social distancing and wearing protective masks, effectively reducing economic activities. Apart from the economic impact the virus has on human activity, the virus has also impacted religious rituals, as people must follow health protocols and adjust certain community-based rituals to home-based. This has been the starting point of change in the Muslim religious activities. In the fiqh literature, this form of leniency in worship is referred to as rukshah, which literally means relief or leniency. The following article is about how the community lifestyles and religious practices have had to adapt due to the Covid-19 pandemic. The findings of this study shall be a contribution in Islamic sociology, which seeks to take a snapshot of the conditions of society in adapting to life during the pandemic and an analysis of Islamic community life patterns after the Covid-19 pandemic

Keywords: Covid-19, Lifestyle, Community .

1. Introduction

The year 2020 is a surprising moment for many people. How come? We are not just facing the fact that the spread of the coronavirus is happening so fast through human mobility and interaction. However, the acceleration of technology is also being felt, where all activities such as work, study, and worship are implemented online.

Muslims have reacted differently to the Covid-19 pandemic, particularly in Indonesia. Bisri used the case and experience of a small Muslim community in Ciamis, West Java, Indonesia, as an example. According to him, the Muslim response to the virus in Ciamis may be divided into five types. The five typologies are irrational-passive, which refers to those who hold beliefs that are not founded on scientific logic while also failing to offer solutions for Covid-19 prevention. Another group shows more character as active-haters but all of their arguments tend to be irrational. The next three groups show rational characters, but some are semi-rational and support government policies, rational but unwilling in presenting their arguments, and finally they are rational-active-supportive. The five categories are influenced by educational background, social life, culture, economy, religious understanding, and religious commitment[1]. The last three groups, who support government programs and are more careful in implementing health protocols during the pandemic, can also be observed from

the behavior of Islamic community organizations (Ormas). Several big Indonesian community organizations have a similar viewpoint, particularly when it comes to religious activity. They also issued fatwas based on other theological grounds at the same time. Every mass organization has its own mass base, which consists of common people. The majority of them follow the policies and legal fatwas given by mass organizations and Islamic religious leaders at the grassroots level. At this level of society, very few people have deviant and different behavior from the mainstream. To anticipate the spread of the virus, most of the mass organizations and their supporters have completely restricted religious activities, such as closing mosques and stopping congregational prayers that cause crowds. Only a few people force themselves to remain active in worship together as before the Covid-19 pandemic [2].

Religionist behavior exacerbates the loss of religious power and authority in the perception of the Indonesian people, as well as religiously connected medical experts, as authoritative sources in offering public prevention advice. Religious organizations and paramedics are also split. Religious groups and paramedics also disagree and are divided. The most recent case is about the halal use of the AstraZeneca vaccine. For example, the East Java Nahdlatul Ulama Regional Board (PWNNU) called the AstraZeneca brand vaccine holy and halal for use. Chairman of the East Java PWNNU KH Marzuki Mustamar said, "The results of the study of the AstraZeneca vaccine are sacred and halal, even though there is an element of pork in the manufacturing process,"[3]. At the same time, LPPOM MUI demonstrated that AstraZeneca's Covid-19 vaccine employs trypsin in its manufacturing process. This scientific investigation was what prompted the Fatwa Commission to rule that the vaccination is haram, but that it can still be administered in an emergency. According to AstraZeneca, the procedure does not use pork. It was discovered through scientific investigations that LPPOM MUI occurs[4].

From various previous studies, the discussion on "how the community lifestyles and religious practices has had to adapt due to the Covid-19 pandemic" has not been widely studied. The most essential causes for the Muslim community's changes in religious practices and lifestyle patterns throughout the transition phase to health standards must be investigated. Religious rituals have altered dramatically during the pandemic compared to before the outbreak, yet for some groups, these activities are being preserved with their distinct discursive arguments. Similarly, the Muslim community's lifestyle has evolved by introducing new patterns, while some have persisted to the old ones.

2. Methods

This type of research is literature review, which involves a step-by-step process of gathering information. The research process itself is carried out by identifying and finding relevant information, analyzing what was found, and then developing and expressing ideas based on the findings. The type of information that is most needed is about the public's response to the application of health protocols during the pandemic as a form of government policy and to the fatwas of official religious institutions such as religious-based community organizations. To find relevant sources, this study uses a literature review, which includes: books, periodicals, newspapers, government documents, biographical sources, videos, reference books, expert views, special archives/collections, and internet sources[5].

After finding conclusions that are representative enough to describe the rational reasons behind the behavior, lifestyle, and religious practices in Indonesia during the pandemic, the researcher sees that there are other aspects that are also important to study, as derivatives of the diversity of rationalizations of these religious communities, namely: social conflict. Apparently, the Indonesian people who have such a diversity of views tend to create conflict. For this reason, conflict theory is also used in this study. Conflict theorists view religion as an institution that helps maintain patterns of social inequality. They try to be critical of the ways in which many religious institutions promote their idea that believers should be content with the way things are, because they are divinely ordained. Conflict theorists also point out that those in power within a religion are often able to dictate practices, rituals, and beliefs through their interpretation of religious texts or through proclaimed direct

communication from the divine [6] This conflict analysis is used to support the analysis of the rational choice of religious attitudes during the pandemic

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. The Obscurity of Government Regulation

According to experts, the problem with the Indonesian government stems from a legal issue that has yet to be resolved. Despite the fact that Covid-19 is an infectious illness with the potential to cause a public health emergency, preventative actions against this type of infectious disease are not taken as soon as feasible. In Indonesia, there is currently no legislation or regulation governing the prevention of infectious illnesses. According to Dalinama Telaumbanua, there are five (5) government rules and eleven (11) necessary health ministry regulations must be adopted in order to combat and avoid the threat of the Covid-19 infectious illness. The two types of regulations are considered very useful by Dalinama Telaumbanua in anticipating health emergencies. With these two rules, legal certainty in preventing the widespread spread of Covid-19 becomes clearer [7].

Although the government implemented more restrictions in the future, experts said that bad narratives propagated more rapidly and the government's response was slow. This was demonstrated when Covid-19 had not yet entered and was approaching Indonesia, and the negative narrative provided by government elites tended to imply that there was no crisis at all, slowing decision-making. Furthermore, there is a lack of coordination, particularly between the central and local governments. This asynchronous coordination makes it difficult to manage the Covid-19. This is worsened by people's lack of understanding and resistance to the government's slow and asynchronous guidance. As a result, preventive initiatives have come to a halt due to a lack of community support. The combination of these three reasons makes the government's efforts to contain the Covid-19 outbreak in Indonesia more difficult[8].

3.2. Polarization of Society's Viewpoint

People must follow health protocols and adapt some community-based rituals to home-based rituals as the Covid-19 pandemic spreads. This marked the beginning of a shift in Muslim religious practices. This type of forbearance in worship is known as *rukshah* in fiqh literature, which literally means alleviation or mercy. The public, on the other hand, is still unfamiliar with the norms of Usul Fiqh *al-masyaqqah al-tajlibu al-taisyiir*, which state that an emergency provides convenience. The public is unfamiliar with the term "emergency," but it has a too restricted definition, which is confined to things that endanger life, such as a lack of food to support life. In practice, *al-masyaqqah* must be tailored to the circumstances. *Al-masyaqqah al-'Azhimmah* and *al-masyaqqah al-Khafifah* are at least two of the criteria. As a result, people's reactions differ when fatwa institutions such as the Indonesian Ulama Council (Majelis Ulama Indonesia/ MUI) issue regulations. Some people agree, while others disagree. Those who agree respond positively to MUI's efforts, while those who disagree publicly and privately refuse[9].

The principle of *rukshah* applies not only to irregular workers and people, but also to medical staff who are in charge of public health. The problem that often arises and is experienced by the medical team is their use of personal protective equipment (PPE). As a result, the MUI issued Fatwa No. 17 of 2020. The MUI has a fatwa that the usage of PPE that does not enable medical professionals to conduct ablution correctly does not need to be removed, based on the religious concept of *rukshah*. The medical team's law comes under the category of *faqid al-tahurain* in such a circumstance. Thus, medical personnel who wear PPE are allowed to perform prayers without ablution or *tayammum* [10].

As a real *rukshah* in carrying out Islamic law, MUI attempted to issue a fatwa involving the temporary prohibition of prayer in mosques. In an ideal situation, Muslims would be obligated to obey their leaders and scholars, especially in vital situations like the pandemic's prevention and management. However, indifference in some sectors, particularly towards the MUI fatwa, has grown in the midst of society. Even though the ulama's fatwas and state policies have been based on the

teachings of the Qur'an, Sunnah, opinions of scholars, and include Maqashid Syariah (the goal of enforcing the law), they reject opinions that allow not to perform Friday prayers and oppose officials who prohibit congregational worship in mosques. And although their legal fatwa does not clash with the Shari'a, people refuse to obey the leader, even if it means preserving human souls. Both leader policies and sharia fatwas pertain to the welfare of the people, both religiously specified benefits and general benefits [11].

In addition to the pros and cons of the fatwas of the ulama related to the guidelines for the implementation of worship, there are also pros and cons to responding to fatwas that are not related to worship, for example regarding vaccinations. The Indonesian Ulama Council (MUI) has issued a fatwa regarding the halal production of Sinovac. The halal fatwa for the Covid-19 vaccine produced by Sinovac is based on the MUI fatwa no. 2 of 2021 by using three fiqh rules, namely *al-dhararu yuzal* (adversity must be eliminated), *al-daf'u awla min al-rafi* (prevention is more important than eliminating) and *yahtamil al-dharar al-khos lidaf'iy al-dhorar al-'am* (bearing/bearing a certain harm in order to prevent the occurrence of eventual harm). These three rules have been found to be accurate and relevant. Muslim health workers are also aware that the MUI fatwa takes into account the rules of fiqh. The side effects of vaccines that have been feared by some people have not been experienced significantly by health workers who have been vaccinated. This increases the level of accuracy of the fiqh rules used by MUI in considering the arguments in its fatwa [12].

Despite the fact that this ulama's fatwa supports government measures aimed at speeding the control of Covid-19 in Indonesia, many individuals have expressed opposing views in various media, even if the debate is still ongoing. On Twitter, for example, the public's reaction to the immunization campaign was mixed. Some were enthusiastic, while others were unfavorable. People who offer a good reaction to the vaccination debate (30%) and those who give a negative response (26 percent). The words that most often appear and show negative sentiments are in the form of public talk about the vaccine controversy which is considered hasty, halal certification of vaccines and public doubts about the quality of the vaccine to be used [13]. When the halal vaccine is out, the pros and cons of this society still have not ended. Sources of opposition can also be grouped into two kinds: first, medical expert. In a webinar on knowledge of the Covid-19 vaccine for health workers held by the Alumni Association of the University of Padjadjaran, Head of the Immunization Task Force of the Indonesian Pediatrician Association, Cissy B. Kartasmita, revealed the various reasons behind the doctors' refusal. As many as 30 percent of health workers refused and stated they were not sure about the safety of the Sinovac vaccine [14]. Second, there are the intellectual and religious communities. The ulama are believed to be continuing to encourage the public to intensify the worship activities. The opposing religious group was underestimated because they made simple observations without in-depth knowledge [15].

The resistance of certain Muslims to the government's public policies and the fatwas of religious organizations' authority drives another kind of social discontent, namely the rise of Islamophobia in public areas. Islam is seen as a source of infections, and the hashtag #coronajihad has gone widespread on social media. By disregarding social distance conventions, the goal of this hashtag is to compel oneself to continue doing religious rites as usual. This has fostered anti-Islamic misinformation and theories that are unrelated to the Covid-19 in any way. At the beginning of the outbreak of Covid-19, the media, council members, and certain elements created an Islamophobic issue that triggered panic and division within the Muslim community in particular and the nation in general. This propaganda connects the spread of the virus to Muslim behavior. The media is awash in images of Muslims praying and Muslim women wearing hijabs going about their normal lives. These photographs provide a subliminal message that links Muslim conduct to the widespread spread of Covid-19 illness. Anti-Islamic groups continue to point the finger upon Muslims as the source of the virus's spread [16].

The public's rejection of religious fatwas and government policy is understandable in some cases. When MUI published Fatwa Number 14 of 2020, for example, popular opinion was diverse. Despite the fact that both sides' arguments are based on religious zeal, their actual outcomes are incompatible. If these disparities are investigated further, they are due to variances in requirements and other

subjective variables that vary according to each person's personality. The public perception that is consistent with the MUI fact and government policies proves to be more effective since it leads to a theological value system that supports the maqashid shari'ah principle. Maqashid Shari'at carries the spirit of horizontal relations, the relationship between humans and humans. Meanwhile, people's perceptions that tend to reject the MUI fatwa and government policies are more directed to the theological-normative value system they hold. These normative values rest on the vertical relationship between humans and God [17].

In contrast, societal polarization cannot be isolated from their learning environment. Their surroundings are high, and the religious instructors they follow come down to help establish a way of life and a mindset among the society [18]. As a result, the environment is the most powerful element affecting society's worldview in terms of adhering to government rules and authoritative ulema fatwas. However, if government laws exacerbate the environment, societal issues will worsen. The government's lack of clarity and indecisiveness in implementing health rules, as well as in enforcing fines on offenders, is one element that may be addressed here. All of this has a negative impact on the social environment

4. Conclusion

During the Covid-19 pandemic, the Indonesian Muslim community's lifestyle began to shift, one of which may be observed is their religious rituals. Religious organizations and certain religious figures have issued fatwas in support of government programs to control and prevent the spread of the Covid-19. However, polarization develops within society, resulting in the emergence of a new sociological category known as pro-government, which tends to oppose the majority.

The development approach to interpreting the smart city framework is increasingly finding its relevance during the Covid-19 pandemic. When health protocols must be implemented and limit face-to-face contact, there is a tremendous change in lifestyle. Changes in interaction patterns can be seen from various aspects of life, worship, business, economy, education, public services, and even friendship. Large-Scale Social Restrictions (PSBB) themselves force people to carry out various activities from a distance from their homes. In the realm of government, digitalization towards smart governance has begun to be promoted. New procedures for public services are made through online services, meaning that the current crisis is accelerating the digitization process. In the field of digital payments economy is increasing rapidly and a tremendous surge for online products

The findings of this study contribute to social studies, particularly the rational action theory and social conflict theory, both of which are utilized as primary approaches. As a result, the study's findings include methodological limitations, such as the inability to touch the dialogical domains, which bring together diverse parties to converse in order to build social integration in various social layers. The next research is recommended to look at the attempts of dialogue between various parties that have become increasingly polarized

References

- [1] H. Husni, H. Bisri, T. A. Tantowie, S. S. Rizal, and A. Azis, "Religious community responses to COVID-19: case study on Muslim small community," *Int. J. Psychosocial Rehabil.*, vol. 24, no. 8, pp. 10439–10446, 2020.
- [2] M. Hidayatullahman, H. Husamah, S. Sudarman, F. Yanti, and I. R. Kusumawati, "Religious Behavior of Indonesian Muslims as Responses to the Covid-19 Pandemic," *Al-Adabiya J. Kebud. dan Keagamaan*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 1–14, 2021, doi: 10.37680/adabiya.v16i1.704.
- [3] A. Faizal, "PWNJ Jatim: Vaksin AstraZeneca Suci dan Halal kendati Terdapat Unsur Babi Saat Pembuatannya," *March 22, 2021*. <https://regional.kompas.com/> (accessed August 5, 2021).
- [4] MUI, "LPPOM MUI Buktikan, Vaksin AstraZeneca Manfaatkan Tripsin dari Babi. March 22, 2021," <https://mui.or.id/> (accessed August 5, 2021), 2021.
- [5] L. L. Richardson, *Introduction To Library Research In German Studies: Language, Literature,*

And Civilization. New York : Routledge, 2018.

- [6] O. Maduro, *Religion and Social Conflicts*. Eugene: Wipf and Stock Publishers, 2005.
- [7] D. Telaumbanua, "Urgensi Pembentukan Aturan Terkait Pencegahan Covid-19 di Indonesia," *QALAMUNA J. Pendidikan, Sos. dan Agama*, vol. 12, no. 01, pp. 59–70, 2020, doi: 10.37680/qalamuna.v12i01.290.
- [8] L. Agustino, "Analysis Of Covid-19 Outbreak Handling Policy: The Experience Of Indonesia," *J. Borneo Adm.*, vol. 16, no. 2, pp. 253–270, 2020, doi: 10.24258/jba.v16i2.685.
- [9] Sahari, "Implementasi Al-Masyaqqoh Al-Tajlibu Al-Taisyir Di Tengah Pandemi Covid-19," *J. AQLAM – J. Islam Plur. –Volume 5, Nomor 2, Desember 2020 IMPLEMENTASI*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 139–151, 2020.
- [10] C. R. M. Amel, "Konsep Rukhsah bagi Tenaga Medis dengan Alat Pelindung Diri saat Menangani Pasien COVID-19," *Al-Qanun J. Pemikir. dan Pembaharuan Huk. Islam*, vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 262–282, 2020, doi: 10.15642/alqanun.2019.22.2.262-282.
- [11] Syamsuddin, "Keringanan (Rukhsah) Meniadakan Shalat Jumat dan Shalat Jama'ah serta Kewajiban Menaati Ulul Amri Syamsuddin," *Al-"adl*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 165–184, 2020.
- [12] I. R. S. Turnip, "Kehalalan Vaksin Covid-19 Produksi Sinovac Dalam Fatwa Mui Dan Implementasi Vaksinasinya Pada Tenaga Kesehatan Di Puskesmas Tanjung Morawa, Deli Serdang (Perspektif Qawaidh Fiqhiyyah)," *J. Huk. Islam dan Pranata Sos. Islam*, vol. 9, no. 01, pp. 59–83, 2021, doi: 10.30868/am.v9i01.1250.
- [13] F. F. Rachman and S. Pramana, "Analisis Sentimen Pro dan Kontra Masyarakat Indonesia tentang Vaksin COVID-19 pada Media Sosial Twitter," *Heal. Inf. Manag. J.*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 100–109, 2020, [Online]. Available: <https://inohim.esaunggul.ac.id/index.php/INO/article/view/223/175>.
- [14] A. Siswadi, "Survei, 20 Persen Tenaga Medis di 4 Kota Ini Tolak Vaksinasi Covid-19," <https://tekno.tempo.co/> (accessed Agustus 6, 2021)., 2021.
- [15] A. S. Notonegoro, "Sains Melampaui Politik dan Agama," *Maarif*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 109–136, 2019.
- [16] M. Bakry, A. Syatar, I. Haq, C. Mundzir, M. Arif, and M. M. Amiruddin, "Arguing islamophobia during COVID-19 outbreaks: A consideration using Khusūs Al-Balwāū," *Int. J. Criminol. Sociol.*, vol. 9, no. June, pp. 2757–2765, 2020, doi: 10.6000/1929-4409.2020.09.340.
- [17] M. F. Imaduddin, "Studi Persepsi Masyarakat Terhadap Fatwa Mui No. 14 Tahun 2020 Tentang Penyelenggaraan Ibadah Dalam Situasi Wabah Covid-19," *JISA J. Ilm. Sosioologi Agama*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 92–113, 2020.
- [18] A. Z. Sarnoto and S. Romli, "Pengaruh Kecerdasan Emosional (EQ) Dan Lingkungan Belajar Terhadap Motivasi Belajar Siswa Sma Negeri 3 Tangerang Selatan," *Andragogi J. Pendidik. Islam dan Manaj. Pendidik. Islam*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 55–75, 2019, doi: 10.36671/andragogi.v1i1.48.

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